

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

DERIVATION OF A NUMERICAL SCHEME FOR FIFTH ORDER INITIAL VALUE PROBLEMS USING MAXIMA

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a derivation of a numerical scheme to solve fifth order initial value problems using the open source computer algebra system MAXIMA.

Keywords: Initial Value Problems, Taylor series, Maximum Absolute Error, Approximation, Lipschitz condition, computer algebra system, MAXIMA.

1. Introduction

An efficient method for solving fifth order initial value problems was proposed by the author with Dinesh Kumar [3] and for third and fourth order initial value problems by the same in [1, 2].

In this paper, we present the MAXIMA code to derive the schemes used in the papers [1, 2, 3]. Here we present the code only for the fifth order IVPs and the schemes in [1, 2] was also derived in the same manner with some minor modifications.

2. The Derivation of the Scheme using MAXIMA

Recall the scheme presented in the paper[3] :

Choose and fix a real number a :

$$a \neq -1.$$

We define the scheme :

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{u_{i+1}} &= u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u'''_i + \frac{h^4}{24}u^{IV}_i + c_1h^5u^V_i + c_2h^6u^{VI}_i \\ \overline{u'_{i+1}} &= u'_i + hu''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u'''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^4}{24}u^V_i + c_1h^5u^{VI}_i \\ \overline{u''_{i+1}} &= u''_i + hu'''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u^V_i + c_1h^4u^{VI}_i \\ \overline{u'''_{i+1}} &= u'''_i + hu^{IV}_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u^V_i + c_1h^3u^{VI}_i \\ \overline{u^{IV}_{i+1}} &= u^{IV}_i + hu^V_i + c_1h^2u^{VI}_i\end{aligned}\tag{2.1}$$

We find $a_0, b_0, c_0, d_0, e_0, c_1, c_2$ so that

$$\begin{aligned}u_{i+1} &= a_0(\overline{u_{i+1}} + au_i) + b_0h(\overline{u'_{i+1}} + au'_i) + c_0h^2(\overline{u''_{i+1}} + au''_i) + d_0h^3(\overline{u'''_{i+1}} + au'''_i) \\ &\quad + e_0h^4(\overline{u^{IV}_{i+1}} + au^{IV}_i)\end{aligned}\tag{2.2}$$

Using Taylor series on the left hand side

$$\begin{aligned}u_{i+1} &= u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u''_i + \frac{h^3}{3!}u'''_i + \frac{h^4}{4!}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^5}{5!}u^V_i + \frac{h^6}{6!}u^{VI}_i + O(h^7) \\ &= a_0\left(u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u'''_i + \frac{h^4}{24}u^{IV}_i + c_1h^5u^V_i + c_2h^6u^{VI}_i + au_i\right) \\ &\quad + b_0h\left(u'_i + hu''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u'''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^4}{24}u^V_i + c_1h^5u^{VI}_i + au'_i\right) \\ &\quad + c_0h^2\left(u''_i + hu'''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u^{IV}_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u^V_i + c_1h^4u^{VI}_i + au''_i\right) \\ &\quad + d_0h^3\left(u'''_i + hu^{IV}_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u^V_i + c_1h^3u^{VI}_i + au'''_i\right) \\ &\quad + e_0h^4\left(u^{IV}_i + hu^V_i + c_1h^2u^{VI}_i + au^{IV}_i\right)\end{aligned}\tag{2.3}$$

Truncating the series and equating the corresponding coefficients of

$$u_i, hu'_i, h^2u''_i, h^3u'''_i, h^4u^{IV}_i, h^5u^V_i, h^6u^{VI}_i$$

on both the sides, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
aa_0 + a_0 &= 1 \\
ab_0 + b_0 + a_0 &= 1 \\
ac_0 + c_0 + b_0 + \frac{a_0}{2} &= \frac{1}{2} \\
ad_0 + d_0 + c_0 + \frac{b_0}{2} + \frac{a_0}{6} &= \frac{1}{6} \\
ae_0 + e_0 + d_0 + \frac{c_0}{2} + \frac{b_0}{6} + \frac{a_0}{24} &= \frac{1}{24} \\
e_0 + \frac{d_0}{2} + a_0c_1 + \frac{c_0}{6} + \frac{b_0}{24} &= \frac{1}{120} \\
c_1e_0 + c_1d_0 + a_0c_2 + c_0c_1 + b_0c_1 &= \frac{1}{720}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

Solving these, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
1 \quad a_0 &= \frac{1}{(1+a)} \\
2 \quad b_0 &= \frac{a}{(1+a)^2} \\
3 \quad c_0 &= \frac{a(a-1)}{2(1+a)^3} \\
4 \quad d_0 &= \frac{a(a^2-4a+1)}{6(a+1)^4} \\
5 \quad e_0 &= \frac{(a-1)a(a^2-10a+1)}{24(a+1)^5} \\
6 \quad c_1 &= \frac{(a^5-25a^4+70a^3-20a^2+5a+1)}{120(a+1)^4} \\
7 \quad c_2 &= -\frac{(37a^9-1000a^8+1260a^7+1654a^6+2236a^5-288a^4-280a^3-10a^2-21a-4)}{2880(a+1)^8}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

To derive the above coefficients in MAXIMA we ran the following code in blue(output not shown here):

```
kill(all);
```

Define the equations (2.1) :

```
ub0:u0+h*u1+(h^2/2)*u2+(h^3/6)*u3+(h^4/24)*u4+(c1*h^5)*u5+
(c2*h^6)*u6;
ub1:u1+h*u2+(h^2/2)*u3+(h^3/6)*u4+(h^4/24)*u5+(c1*h^5)*u6;
ub2:u2+h*u3+(h^2/2)*u4+(h^3/6)*u5+(c1*h^4)*u6;
ub3:u3+h*u4+(h^2/2)*u5+(c1*h^3)*u6;
ub4:u4+h*u5+(c1*h^2)*u6;
```

Define the equation (2.2) :

```
uNew:a0*(ub0+a*u0)+b0*h*(ub1+a*u1)+c0*h^2*(ub2+a*u2)+
d0*h^3*(ub3+a*u3)+e0*h^4*(ub4+a*u4);
```

```
q:expand(uNew);
```

Define the LHS equation (2.3) :

```
uNewT:u0+h*u1+(h^2/2)*u2+(h^3/6)*u3+(h^4/24)*u4+(h^5/120)*u5+
(h^6/720)*u6;
```

Form the equation (2.3) :

```
eq:makelist(coeff(q, h, k)=coeff(uNewT, h, k), k, 0, 6);
```

Solve the equations (2.4) and simplify them :

```
sol:solve(eq, [a0, b0, c0, d0, e0, c1, c2] );
f:factor(sol);
```

Print the solutions (2.5) :

```
for i:1 thru 7 do print(f[1][i]);
```

3. Expressions for Derivatives

The expressions for the first, second, third and fourth order derivatives in [3] are:

$$\begin{aligned}
u'_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u_{i+1}} - u_i}{120c_2h} \right) + \left(\frac{120c_2 - 1}{120c_2} \right) u'_i + \left(\frac{240c_2 - 1}{240c_2} \right) hu''_i + \left(\frac{360c_2 - 1}{720c_2} \right) h^2 u'''_i + \left(\frac{480c_2 - 1}{2880c_2} \right) h^3 u^{IV}_i \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{5c_2 - c_1}{120c_2} \right) h^4 u^V_i \\
u''_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u'_{i+1}} - u'_i}{24c_1h} \right) + \left(\frac{24c_1 - 1}{24c_1} \right) u''_i + \left(\frac{48c_1 - 1}{48c_1} \right) hu'''_i + \left(\frac{72c_1 - 1}{144c_1} \right) h^2 u^{IV}_i + \left(\frac{96c_1 - 1}{576c_1} \right) h^3 u^V_i \\
u'''_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u''_{i+1}} - u''_i}{6c_1h} \right) + \left(\frac{6c_1 - 1}{6c_1} \right) u'''_i + \left(\frac{12c_1 - 1}{12c_1} \right) hu^{IV}_i + \left(\frac{18c_1 - 1}{36c_1} \right) h^2 u^V_i \\
u^{IV}_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u'''_{i+1}} - u'''_i}{2c_1h} \right) + \left(\frac{2c_1 - 1}{2c_1} \right) u^{IV}_i + \left(\frac{4c_1 - 1}{4c_1} \right) hu^V_i \quad (3.1)
\end{aligned}$$

where $u^V_i = f_i$.

The above equalities were verified by the following :

Assign the constants c_1, c_2 :

c1:rhs(f[1][6]);

c2:rhs(f[1][7]);

The equation for the first derivative in (3.1) :

D1:(1/(120*c2*h))*(ub0-u0)+(1-(1/(120*c2)))*u1+(1-(1/(240*c2)))*h*u2
+((1/2)-(1/(720*c2)))*h^2*u3+((1/6)-(1/(120*24*c2)))*h^3*u4
+((1/24)-(c1/(120*c2)))*h^4*u5\$

expand(ratsimp(D1));

The equation for the second derivative in (3.1) :

D2:(1/(24*c1*h))*(ub1-u1)+(1-(1/(24*c1)))*u2+(1-(1/(48*c1)))*h*u3
+((1/2)-(1/(24*6*c1)))*h^2*u4+((1/6)-(1/(24*24*c1)))*h^3*u5\$

expand(ratsimp(D2));

The equation for the thid derivative in (3.1) :

D3:(1/(6*c1*h))*(ub2-u2)+(1-(1/(6*c1)))*u3+(1-(1/(12*c1)))*h*u4
+((1/2)-(1/(36*c1)))*h^2*u5\$

expand(ratsimp(D3));

The equation for the fourth derivative in (3.1) :

D4:(1/(2*c1*h))*(ub3-u3)+(1-(1/(2*c1)))*u4+(1-(1/(4*c1)))*h*u5\$

expand(ratsimp(D4));

References

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